

THE ROLE OF STEM ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Aida STOIAN

Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova,
aidda1977@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Classes in the STEM science category include biology, ecology, chemistry and physics. However, STEM science classes also incorporate technology, engineering, and math into science studies. STEM education or STEM learning refers to school curricula for the three levels of education, preschool, primary, secondary, that are designed to help students acquire the skills needed to succeed in the 21st century job market, which includes a wide variety of transversal skills: critical thinking, problem solving, teamwork, adaptability, creativity, digital literacy and so on. However, STEM is not a separate subject. STEM-based learning programs aim to increase students' interest in pursuing higher education and careers in these fields.

Keywords: STEM education, problem solving, teamwork, adaptability, creativity, digital literacy.

Introduction

STEM is an abbreviation for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics.

STEM components refer to:

STEM science. Classes in the STEM science category include biology, ecology, chemistry, and physics. However, STEM science classes also incorporate technology, engineering, and math into science studies.

STEM technology. Technology classes may include digital modeling and prototyping, 3D printing, mobile technology, computer programming, data analysis, machine learning, and game development.

STEM engineering. Engineering classes may include civil engineering, electronics, electrical engineering, mechanical engineering, and robotics.

STEM math. Math is a STEM category with classes such as algebra, geometry, and calculus. STEM math also incorporates concepts and exercises that apply science, technology, and engineering to mathematics.

SEM education or STEM learning refers to school curricula for the three levels of education, preschool, primary, secondary:

1. They are designed to help students acquire skills necessary to succeed in the job market;

2. Includes a variety of transversal skills: critical thinking, problem solving, teamwork; adaptability, creativity, digital literacy;

STEM-based curricula are designed to increase students' interest in continuing higher education and careers in these fields;

The STEM teaching model has been developed through the studies of Jean-Marie De Ketele and Xavier Roegiers since the 1980.

The theoretical and practical basis for the implementation of integrated interdisciplinary teaching in schools was developed by the scientific community and promoted at the UNESCO conference in France in 1986.

According to Roegiers (2004), there is no natural state that corresponds and can be described by a single field of natural sciences.

Any state of nature can be proven to be related to two or more fields of study and dividing into separate fields or subjects is a tool we use to investigate a particular phenomenon in depth.

First of all, there is no direct correspondence between an object of research and a single field of natural sciences.

Secondly, focusing on a single field means diminishing our understanding of the object of research, while a deeper understanding becomes possible by applying methods from a variety of fields – in short, an interdisciplinary approach.

The interdisciplinary approach opposes the division into individual subjects for the purpose of analyzing and understanding natural phenomena (Roegiers, 2004)

Thus, according to Roegiers (2004), if a school divides natural sciences into separate subjects to be taught, there is a danger that students - despite understanding the theory underlying each subject - will not be able to apply their knowledge in real situations and everyday life.

Methodology

As mentioned before, as mentioned above, STEM is an interdisciplinary approach to learning where academic concepts are coupled with real-world lessons

"Whenever designing STEM activities, the real world should be the main entry point" (Hill, 1998).

Students apply science, technology, engineering, and math in contexts that make connections between the classroom and the world around them.

STEM comprises the following major areas of study:

Natural, physical and life sciences (sometimes including medicine, sometimes not)

Computers, electronics and other technology-related topics

All types of engineering

Mathematics or any field involving intensive application of mathematical principles

Some STEM definitions include social sciences such as psychology, economics, and anthropology. However, most sources consider these categories separate.

STEM education typically uses a blended learning model that combines traditional classroom teaching with online learning and hands-on activities. This model aims to allow students to experiment with different ways of learning and problem solving.

While the student should be the main character in their own learning, the teacher has the critical role of orchestrating each child's learning process (Crawford, 2000).

Using a sports metaphor, the teacher should feel less like the team captain and more like a coach during a match: be allowed to watch and guide, but not interfere.

The teacher's questions should provoke deeper thinking, make new questions arise (Mant, 2017). In fact, he should avoid giving closed answers that could turn children's work into a search for the "right" answer that the teacher already knows (Dejonckheere, Vervaeke, & Van De Keere, 2016).

Throughout the process, both teacher and students must keep in mind the importance of assessment (Hodgson, 2010).

Self-assessment through rubrics helps students understand what they are learning and what they are accomplishing. The pair rating allows them to reflect on the work of their teams, but also on their own performance.

On the other hand, the teacher – who has become a coach – can (and should) dedicate himself to observing the children and giving them feedback on their work. The teacher should talk to the children both to test and improve their understanding of the concepts they acquire and the skills they develop. (Zemelman, Daniels, & Hyde, 2005).

Working in STEM means facing challenges that usually require teamwork.

Collaborative learning is naturally rooted in STEM (Zemelman, Daniels, & Hyde, 2005) and allows each team member to give the group a different skill.

The open nature of STEM makes progress and improvement possible for all children, from high-achieving students to students with learning difficulties, each with their own sets of goals for the group to succeed (Bargerhuff, 2013) (Sanders, 2009).

Discussions

Benefits of STEM

1. Media and technological literacy

Media literacy refers to an individual's ability to make informed judgments about the content they receive from different media, while technological literacy is an individual's ability to adapt quickly to new technologies and use appropriately according to their needs. Media literacy and technology literacy are interconnected.

Children need to learn how to discuss, analyze, verify the information they receive from different sources, from an early age.

2. Boosts critical thinking skills

For example, adaptability and resilience, communication skills, critical thinking, and other skills that boost an employee's productivity are what a recruiter is looking for.

STEM education helps children develop these soft skills from early and middle childhood because it requires children to think

about problems and find solutions, leading to better memory, improved cognitive skills, and overall brain health.

3. Stimulates curiosity

Children are encouraged to develop more scientific questions that turn into investigations.

STEM education will help them find some of the answers based on what they learn through lessons. By exemplifying real-world facts, encouraging questions, and developing independence, STEM education heightens children's curiosity.

4. The growing need for workers in STEM fields.

Today, most careers require a certain amount of knowledge in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

Our communities need a well-trained workforce to fill vacancies, stimulate the economy and build for the future. That's why STEM education is vital: it's about being prepared for college, job opportunities, and life.

5. STEM education closes the gender gap

Bridging the gender gap is not only a moral issue, but also a way of economic prosperity

STEM education for all children from an early age is the first step in encouraging girls to address this issue.

6. STEM education helps children become future entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurship and STEM learning go hand in hand.

The soft skills children learn through STEM education are necessary to become successful entrepreneurs. STEM learning resources provide children with practical skills to succeed in entrepreneurship

7. STEM skills make children easier to recruit Children need to prepare for jobs that are not yet in the labour market

To do this, we need to teach children how to adapt to a changing world. This is another issue that is effectively addressed through STEM education: becoming more recruitable with the skill sets they acquire.

8. Higher average salary.

Last but not least, the factor to emphasize about the importance of STEM education is the average annual salary that STEM workers receive.

STEM creates connections within the curriculum, providing a solid foundation to support learning. With an exceptional disposition, students can and do achieve the highest levels of success.

STEM education emphasizes the importance of problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, curiosity, decision-making, leadership, entrepreneurship, embracing failure (and learning from it), and more.

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